

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE PROFESSIONOGRAM OF A MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHER

Solovei Anna

*Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University
28 Sadova Street, Uman, Ukraine, 20300*

Abstract

The article deals with one of the most important components in the formation of professional competence of a foreign language teacher, namely, cross-cultural communicative competence. The so-called "cultural thesaurus" of a specialist is described, which includes such concepts as "culture", "pedagogical culture", "communication culture", "cultural patterns, norms and values", "lifestyle", "cultural activities", "professional interests". It is noted that culture is an important criterion for the quality of education, since socio-cultural changes in education have determined the importance of problems of culture and pedagogical activity of subjects of the educational process. It is considered as one of the defining components of the new anthropocentric concept of modern education. The requirements for the implementation of the cultural approach to professional training of foreign language teachers are outlined, the theoretical basis of the cultural approach in the training of future foreign language teachers is summarized. It is revealed that the personal resource, which includes a set of general cultural knowledge, skills, and abilities, is the basis for the formation of a teacher's cross-cultural competence.

Keywords: cross-cultural communicative competence, foreign language culture, intercultural and transcultural consciousness of the graduate, cultural thesaurus, pedagogical culture.

In the era of cultural dialogue and new language policy in Europe, one of the priority competencies of a future foreign language teacher is cross-cultural competence. According to the foreign language program for language institutions of higher education, the formation of cross-cultural communicative competence is one of the practical goals of teaching [3]. Cross-cultural communicative competence is understood as the ability of a person to successfully and adequately communicate in a foreign language in situations of intercultural communication of various types and kinds, taking into account the main external socio-cultural and internal situational factors. Taking into account the fact that Ukraine has finally chosen the path of entry into the European educational and cultural space, integration with European countries, internationalization of business relations in various fields of human activity, the issue of effective possession of intercultural competence becomes particularly relevant for the future teacher of a foreign language, who should not only possess this type of competence, but also be a retranslator of foreign language culture for his potential students. It is the foreign language teacher who should become a key figure in the implementation of the new language policy in Europe and Ukraine. The problem of integrating cultural components into the process of teaching a foreign language was considered in the works of O. Tarnopolsky, J. Harmer, M. Wallace and others [2].

As it can be noted, effective interaction between teachers and students is a necessary channel through which the social organization of student behaviour is carried out. It is known that favourable relations between teachers and students in the educational process are especially necessary for the formation of positive qualities of the student's personality and professional

improvement of the teacher. The most important condition for establishing speech action between a teacher and a student is communicative activity, which is largely manifested in foreign language lessons. When learning a foreign language, four learning goals are expected to be achieved: practical, educational, developmental, and educational. The practical goal in teaching a foreign language occupies a prominent position and provides for practical mastery of speaking skills at a level sufficient for communication in all types of speech activity. The culture of communication in foreign language lessons depends to a large extent on the teacher's speech activity, knowledge of the norms of speech etiquette, especially authentic ones. Therefore, the new state program in foreign languages for universities pays great attention to achieving the intercultural and transcultural consciousness of the graduate. During the training of foreign language teachers, it is necessary to pay attention to the correctness of speech behaviour in the process of communication, namely: correct and competent speech; strict adequacy of statements, specific features of speech behaviour of native speakers. During practical language classes, special attention should be paid to students' mastery of classroom expressions; normativity, emotional and expressive colouring of speech; features of the national speech etiquette of native speakers, through which the principle of politeness is implemented. Knowledge of the peculiarities of English speech communication etiquette will help to avoid curious situations of inadequate speech behaviour of the future teacher. During the period of speech practice classes, it is important to teach students how to use the formulas of cultural speech behaviour of native speakers, form the sociolinguistic competence of the future teacher, and improve professional and speech activities. Knowing a foreign language, students often

use non-authentic expressions in their speech activities with students, which leads to a decrease in the overall culture of communication in a foreign language. Thus, the purpose of practical training of a future teacher is the formation of professional language competence, which will allow for better organization of interaction between participants in the educational pedagogical process at school [1].

In the context of professional training of a foreign language teacher, the cultural approach is a set of methodological techniques that provide an analysis of professional training through the prism of system-forming cultural concepts that form the "cultural thesaurus" of a specialist ("culture", "pedagogical culture", "communication culture", "cultural patterns, norms and values", "lifestyle", "cultural activity", "professional interests"); it allows you to provide the foundation for the formation and development of the culture of pedagogical work.

Culture is an important criterion for the quality of education, since socio-cultural changes in education have determined the importance of problems of culture and pedagogical activity of subjects of the educational process as one of the defining components of the new anthropocentric concept of modern education, acts as the basis for the formation of pedagogical morality and means its orientation to a person as an integral, active, humane, spiritual person, carrier of moral norms and values; professional activity of a teacher is based on the unity of spiritual, moral and technological components of his pedagogical culture [6].

The most important requirements for implementing a cultural approach to professional training of foreign language teachers in universities are:

- cultural conformity, which involves taking into account national and world cultural experience in the field of teaching foreign languages in the content of training;
- humanitarian dialogic as a form of intersubjective communication;
- integrative activity that combines scientific knowledge at the intersection of philology, psychology, pedagogy and other humanities, synthesizing and systematizing complex data of these sciences from a common point of view.

The implementation of the axiological approach to professional training of foreign language teachers in universities is determined by the strengthening of the axiological and cultural component of pedagogical activity, which acts as guidelines for professional behaviour of teachers. The axiological approach considers the professional competence of a teacher of foreign languages through a system of values as generalized basic ideas about the goals and norms of professional behaviour, guidelines that exist in the teacher's mind and which are characterized by signs of significance, normativity, necessity, expediency, justice, etc. So, the formation of professional competence of applicants for higher education is possible only if it is understood as a value phenomenon, a system of values that have personal significance. Thus, the axiological approach makes it possible to consider the professional training

of foreign language teachers as a process aimed at mastering the system of professional values, which is manifested in its historical formation and fixation in the public consciousness. Within the framework of this approach, a hierarchical system of professional values of teachers is defined. The axiological approach considers the professional training of teachers for the new Ukrainian school through a system of moral and ethical (dignity, honesty, justice, care, respect for life, respect for oneself and other people) and socio-political (freedom, democracy, cultural diversity, respect for the native language and culture, patriotism, respect for the environment, respect for the law, solidarity, responsibility) values, which should be formed by future specialists for further transfer of these values to school-children [4].

The theoretical basis of the cultural approach in the training of future foreign language teachers can be summarized in the following provisions:

- the content of education includes such interrelated components as: creating conditions for equal dialogue with the ethno-cultural environment; providing everyone with the opportunity to identify themselves as a representative of a certain national culture and traditions;
- formation of tolerant consciousness, multicultural thinking of a future foreign language teacher and appropriate behaviour skills;
- curricula and teaching as well as methodical complexes should include materials aimed at preserving and developing the entire wealth and diversity of cultures, and should not include materials that humiliate other nations and ethnic groups, social groups;
- certain requirements are put forward for a foreign language teacher: a high level of general cultural competence, the ability to actively apply innovative technologies of cultural orientation, possession of means of effective interpersonal and intercultural communication, social responsibility, the desire for spiritual self-development, creative self-realization [5].

Therefore, an important factor in improving the general level of culture of the future teacher of foreign languages is the development of his general cultural competence as a personal and professional characteristic of a specialist, demonstrating his readiness to attract future students to the cultural context of the educational subject "Foreign Language", to ensure their general cultural development, the focus of the educational process on the interests of the individual of those who study. The formation of general cultural competence of future teachers of foreign languages, the development of their general and pedagogical culture is a complex multidimensional problem that has been studied in the works of domestic and foreign scientists.

So, the general cultural competence of a future foreign language teacher is an integrative personal resource, which includes a set of general cultural knowledge, skills, and abilities; a system of general cultural competencies that a future specialist should master; cultural experience of the individual; culturally oriented special professional knowledge; knowledge of ways and norms of using language in various situations of communication and pedagogical activity, experience

of communication, as well as personal attitude to a foreign language culture, including the ability of a person to resolve socio-cultural conflicts in communication, overcome cross-cultural barriers, the potential for personal development in the process of mastering the language that is being studied. General cultural competence allows an individual to freely navigate the socio-cultural environment, operate with its elements and use it in their own pedagogical activities [5].

References

1. Barno O. M. Theoretical and methodological principles of forming the competence of future English language teachers. Scientific notes of the National University of Ostroh Academy. Series: Philological, Ostroh: Publishing House of the National University of Ostroh Academy. 2015. Issue 54. P. 5-9 [Published in Ukrainian]
2. Kalinin V. A. Formation of cross-cultural competence of a future foreign language teacher based on collaborative learning. Scientific notes of the National University of Ostroh Academy. Series: Philological. Publishing House of the National University of Ostroh Academy. 2015. Issue 54. P. 36-38. [Published in Ukrainian]
3. English language program for universities and institutes (five-year course of study): project. Vinnytsia: Novaya kniga publ.. 2001. 245 p. [Published in Ukrainian]
4. Taylor Mark. Teaching Generation Next: A Pedagogy for Today's Learner's. A Collection of Papers on Self-Study and Instructional Improvement. 26th Edition. 2010. P. 192-196
5. Yablokov S. V. Formation of general cultural competence of future foreign language teachers based on an innovative approach in education. The content of philological education in the system of English teachers and philologists professional training: monograph. Ed. Yuliya Fedorova. Sofia: VUZF Publishing House "St. Grigorii Bogosov". 2020. P. 89-113 [Published in Ukrainian]
6. Zadorozhna-Knyahnitska L. V., Netroba M. N. Scientific approaches to professional training of English language teachers. Scientific journal of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. Kiev: Publishing House of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University. 2019. Issue 66 (155). P. 70-74 [Published in Ukrainian]